

**RIGHT TO DEVELOPMENT AND THE NEW INTERNATIONAL
ECONOMIC ORDER: A GLOBAL SOUTH PERSPECTIVE IN LIGHT
OF SPIRITUAL HUMANISM**

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ABSTRACT

This research paper will help us better understand the Declaration of the Right to Development and the New International Economic Order in the light of spiritual humanism. It also shows the importance of the Global economy, which is important for us. What challenges exist in our economy, and how these norms would effectively work for a specific country or group, and for the whole of us. This paper also covers the evolution of the Declaration on the Right to Development and the New International Economic Order since the 1st world War and how the country realized there should be a law for all countries, also known as International Law.

This research paper is prepared in the light of the United Charter, Universal Declaration of Human Rights, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, and International Covenant of Social, Cultural and Political Rights, the role of non-aligned movements, and how they are helpful for us to achieve the idea of globalization in light of Spiritual Humanism.

Keywords: Right to Development, New International Economic Order, International Human Rights Law, Global Economic Justice, Non-Aligned Movement (NAM), Spiritual Humanism.

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I. Introduction

We are living in the 21st century, which is the Globalization era. It means there is no boundary limit for spreading our ideas, skills, technologies, culture, and business, subject to legal norms, which are essential for “right to development”. Right to development does not only mean to increase wealth, services, goods, and infrastructure of our country, but also means to develop these things by fair and just means, following all the norms that have been made on the international level, and also to keep compassion and maintain dignity towards other nations. The main aim of the developing countries of the Global South is to develop themselves to compete with the developed nations. Countries that were colonized or neo- colonized by other countries still focus on development because they are not on the same footing as the developed countries, like the USA, UK, etc. After the 2nd World War, all countries, whether they participated or not, faced economic and financial trauma directly or indirectly. Even though we live in different countries, we are on the same planet, Earth. After the end of the 2nd world War, countries realized that there should be a Law for all nations, and they brought the UN Charter on 26th June 1945 in San Francisco. And 50 countries took part, but Poland also took part in that organization, and they became 51 in number.¹ The UN charter shows unity between all nations, and its Preamble starts with the sentence “WE THE PEOPLES OF THE UNITED NATIONS”.² It shows that we are part of one nation and must help each other. After the enactment of the UN Charter, the General Assembly of the United Nations adopted many conventions for the promotion and development of all the nations and maintained the economic balance among all the nations. The General Assembly of the United Nations proclaimed a watershed document, which is the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), on 10 December 1948, for the protection of all individuals of nations and special treatment for the vulnerable.³

International Convention on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights adopted on 16th December 1966 by General Assembly resolution 2200A (XXI), but it came into force on 3 January 1976, in accordance with Article 27.⁴ Preamble of the International Convention on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) grants inalienable Human Rights and also deals with the protection of the inherent dignity of the individual and declares that all members of the world

¹ Charter of the United Nations, Preamble.

² *Ibid*

³ United nation, United Declaration of Human Right“ <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>.

⁴ *Ibid*

are entitled to Freedom, Justice, and tranquility.⁵ This convention basically strengthens the UDHR. It means that ICESCR supplements the UDHR. International Convention on civil and Political right (ICCPR) was adopted on 16th December 1966 by the General Assembly of United Nation in 2200A (XXI) resolution, but it comes into enforce on 23rd March 1976 and its aim to protect the human right and they enjoy all the right which given by other convention without any barrier or hindrance and the also develop himself.⁶ Where individuals focus on their own development, the country will undoubtedly grow. But if they create themselves by using the proper means and following all the legal norms that have been made on an international level, then they will undoubtedly grow. Still, this development is not merely development; rather, it is more than development that is sustainable development, where people not only focus on development but also keep in mind others' rights and norms that have been implemented.

The Declaration of the Right to Development (herein referred to as DRTD) of 1986 is an inspiring and pious document, which assures all countries and their citizens the right to development subject to legal norms. This declaration offers individuals the right to spread their skills, knowledge, and technologies worldwide. This declaration promotes the concept of globalization, which gives freedom to individuals and countries to spread their innovation or creativity across the world. The same has no territorial limit but is subject to legal norms. Indeed, where individuals develop themselves by following legal means, there is a minimal chance of creating barriers for others. The purpose of DRTD is to maintain balance between all the nations and reduce inequality between them. The General Assembly adopted DRTD on 4 December 1986.⁷ The purpose of this Charter is to build a cooperative and harmonious relationship between them, develop themselves with the protection of human rights, and prevent discrimination based on race, sex, language, and religion. Everyone can develop themselves.⁸ If there is no discrimination on the same grounds. DRTD considers the peace, security, and integrity of the nation.⁹ It shows a balance between globalization and the safety of the country because if a state only focuses on Globalization for the promotion of DRTD, then there are chances of a threat to security. DRTD imposes the obligation on the state to create a congenial environment for the development of individuals.¹⁰ An amiable environment

⁵ International covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, Preamble.

⁶ International covenant on civil and political Rights, Preamble

⁷ UN General Assembly, „Declaration on the Right to Development“ UNGA Res 41/128 (4 December 1986).

⁸ UNGA Res 41/128 (4 December 1986), „Declaration on the Right to Development“ Preamble.

⁹ *Ibid.*

¹⁰ *Ibid.*

is essential for developing not only individuals, but also countries. We are directly or indirectly interconnected, and if any of them creates a nuisance, it would hinder us from achieving our goal of development. The state should be aware of its individuals about human rights and protection of human rights, and also aware of the new international economic order at the global level.¹¹ The General Assembly of the United Nations made a declaration for the creation of the New International Economic Order on 1 May 1977. This declaration aims to strengthen the other declarations that focus on maintaining equality on an international level, like DRTD, UDHR, ICCPR, ICESCR, etc.

II. Historical Development of Universal Declaration of the Right: Development and New International Economic Order

Before the 1st World War (28 July 1914 to 11 November 1918), there were no legal norms for all the Countries at the international level, but after the end of the 1st world War, countries realized that there should be a law for all nations, and they established the League of Nations in 1920. This notion was proposed by the President of Europe, Woodrow Wilson, for an unbiased peace between the nations, but the United States never became a member of the League of Nations.¹² This association could not prevent the 2nd world War (1 September 1939 to 2 September 1945), and this was the biggest battle in history. Countries realized that there should be a milestone association at the international level, which could prevent the same. In San Francisco, representatives of 50 States met and completed the Charter of the United Nations, where all members of the United Nations would become members of the General Assembly and five permanent and six non-permanent members of the Security Council. The United Nations came into existence on 24 October 1945.¹³

DRTD (Declaration on the Right to Development) was adopted on 4 December 1986. Still, Right to Development is already exist in UN CHARTER which is “With a view to the creation of conditions of stability and well-being which are necessary for peaceful and friendly relations among nations based on respect for the principle of equal rights and self- determination of peoples, the United Nations shall promote: a. higher standards of living, full employment, and

¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹² Office of the Historian, „The League of Nations, 1920“ (History.state.gov) <https://history.state.gov/milestones/1914-1920/league> accessed 22 August 2025.

¹³ Office of the Historian, „The Formation of the United Nations, 1945“ <https://history.state.gov/milestones/1937-1945/un> accessed 22 August 2025.

conditions of economic and social progress and development; **b.** solutions of international economic, social, health, and related problems; and international cultural and educational cooperation; and **c.** universal respect for, and observance of, human rights and fundamental freedoms for all without distinction as to race, sex, language, or religion”.¹⁴ The motive of this provision is that all countries should develop by fair means and mechanisms, and also not create any hurdle or barrier for other countries. DRTD is not only based on the UN Charter but also on UDHR, ICESCR, ICCPR.¹⁵

Over time, the United Nations regarded “development” as constituting “social development” and “economic development” while highlighting their interrelatedness. In 1952, the UN General Assembly showed its view that social development and its technical assistance should go hand in hand with economic development and its help in matters related to the economy.¹⁶ Both the economic and social parts are interconnected; if one develops and the other doesn’t, it creates an imbalance in society, and the part that develops would not have much effect because both are interconnected. Likewise, the UN Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) stipulated the principle to help the government, whereby the interrelated character of economic and social development goes hand in hand and maintains the balance at the level of the world economy, thereby people improve their standard of living.¹⁷ It shows that social and economic factors are interconnected with each other; one cannot develop without the other.

In 1957, the UN General Assembly integrated the right of humans with economic and social development and declared that the balance of integrated social and economic development must maintain peace, security, and social progress in the light of human freedom, thereby they enjoy their liberty and freedom without any barrier or hindrance.¹⁸

In the mid-1960s, the UN Commission on Human Rights considered the barriers that are related to development along with human rights and created a hindrance in the enjoyment of economic and social rights of developing countries.¹⁹

In 1970, the UN Commission appointed a special Rapporteur, Iranian diplomat Manouchehr

¹⁴ UN Charter art 55.

¹⁵ Yuefen Li, Daniel Uribe and Danish, „The International Discourse on the Right to Development and the Need to Reinvent its Implementation” (South Centre, 8 March 2022) ch 2.

¹⁶ Yuefen Li, Daniel Uribe and Danish, „The International Discourse on the Right to Development and the Need to Reinvent Its Implementation” (South Centre, 8 March 2022) 4.

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ *Ibid.*

Ganji, to prepare a report on the protection of social, cultural, and economic rights, which was given in UDHR and ICESCR, in which greater emphasis was placed on the role of the commission.²⁰ Generally, if any authority is created without any monitoring by any other authority, then it would become corrupt; that is why monitoring is essential. The report, which analyzed the Gnji, was submitted to the 30th Commission in 1974, and the discussion took place for the adoption of the New International Economic Order and Charter for the New Economic Order, thereby strengthening the idea of the Right to Development.²¹

The tussle between North and South exists because the South countries want NIEO (New International Economic Order), but the North countries were making counterarguments against NIEO. The economic order at the international level was not good, and the country was facing the problem of economic stagnation with inflation, which was not good, especially for developing or underdeveloped countries. Developed countries (North region) were contending against NIEO because they were thinking that if this policy were implemented, then it would be only suitable for creating and not for developed countries, but the aim of this policy was not to restrain the growth of developed countries; instead, it aims to stabilize the balance at the International level regarding economic order.²²

III. Role Of Non-Aligned Movement in The Context of The Right to Development

The Non-Aligned Movement (herein referred to as NAM) was founded in Belgrade. Indian Prime Minister Pandit J L Nehru played a vital role in this movement along with Indonesia's President Suka, Egypt's President Nasser, Ghana's President Kwame Nkrumah, and Yugoslavia's President Josip Broz Tito. B. Tito, but the conference was attended by 25 countries. They also declared that it is not an association or organization, but rather a movement.²³

The newly independent countries were facing the problem of international politics, and they were not ready to compromise on their sovereignty. The social, cultural, political, and

²⁰ *Ibid.*

²¹ *Ibid.*

²² Dr Priya Saroj and Puja Sharma, "The New International Economic Order (NIEO): Challenges and Perspectives" *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, ch 2.

²³ Aruna R Mital, „Non-Aligned Movement and Its Relevance Today“ (2016) 2(7) *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research* 22, 23 (Introduction).

economic issues of these countries were similar, which is why they came together for the protection and promotion of their interest.²⁴

At the beginning of NAM, the Cold War was at its peak, and both military alliances were seeking support from other countries that are less developed or less powerful, and also these countries were scared of their sovereignty and integrity from these powerful nations, and they decided to come together and resolve these issues.²⁵ For the smooth functioning of these movements, they certain principles for the countries that can join these movements, which are given below-

- Autonomous foreign policy.
- Self-governing state.
- It is not aligned with any power bloc that is connected either directly or indirectly with the Cold War.
- Mutual respect for the nation's sovereignty and its territory.
- No indulgence in other countries' personal affairs.
- Non-aggression.
- Maintain and promote equality, benefit, and cooperation for the entire nation.²⁶

These 10 principles are known as Bandung, and later they also became the objective of NAM. Their aim is to build relations among participating countries and work for the benefit of all the nations.²⁷

The main objective of NAM is to focus on the self-independence of non-aligned countries and maintain their sovereignty from the powerful nations. This movement also struggles against the interference of non-aligned countries, apartheid, racism, and imperialism. This movement struggles to promote democratization at the international level and socio-economic development of each country and does all such things that help maintain unity between all the nations and promote equality among all the nations. They also focus on preserving unity among less powerful nations; otherwise, there are chances of endangering our sovereignty and

²⁴ *Ibid.*

²⁵ *Ibid.*

²⁶ Aruna R Mital, „Non-Aligned Movement and Its Relevance Today“ (2016) 2(7) International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research 22, 23 (Introduction).

²⁷ *Ibid.*

internal affairs, hampering growth, and we would be far from enjoying the right to development.

After the Lusaka conference in 1970, the member nations passed a resolution among us to resolve the peaceful dispute between us and abstention from arms or any such kind of article which creates similarity like aggressive association.²⁸

During the 1980s, NAM performed a very crucial role for all the world by promoting the New International Economic Order and allowing the countries to utilize their natural resources without any kind of hindrance from other powerful countries, thereby all the countries would be able to use his own resources without any kind of hindrance from other country which help in maintaining a balance in World economy. The 7th summit of this movement happened in New Delhi, India, which declared the most significant peace movement in the world. It not only maintained a relationship among non-aligned countries but also helped promote the world economy.²⁹

The primary purpose of NAM was to protect ourselves from the Cold War. At the end of the 1980s and early 1990s, a coalition of socialist and communist states, led by the Soviet Union, led to the end of the Cold War. This movement was brought about due to the Cold War, and after the end of the Cold War, it has no relevance.³⁰

IV. Legal Norms of Declaration of Right to Development and New International Economic Order in Light of Spertulism

As we know, the Declaration on the Right to Development 1986 was adopted on 4 December 1986 by the General Assembly of the United Nations. It consists of 10 articles.³¹ As we know, this document is not compulsory binding on all countries, but it imposes a moral obligation on all nations to follow all these principles, which are given under this auspicious document. This declaration is not made to promote any specific country or group but rather to encourage the development of all nations.

²⁸ Aruna R Mital, "Non-Aligned Movement and Its Relevance Today" (2016) 2(7) *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research* 22, 23 (Objectives).

²⁹ Aruna R Mital, "Non-Aligned Movement and Its Relevance Today" (2016) 2(7) *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research* 22, 23 (Objectives).

³⁰ *Ibid.*

³¹ United Nations General Assembly, *Declaration on the Right to Development* UNGA Res 41/128 (4 December 1986).

The Preamble of this document recognizes the global development in the area of economic, social, cultural, and political, and focuses on the aim of sustained development of not only specific individuals or specific groups of individuals or nations, but also the sustained development of all countries, even individuals, it considers the right of individual as per the Union declaration of Human Right 1948 and as well other declaration, recalling all the provision of international covenant of United Nation, specialized agencies related with prevention from discrimination, maintaining peace and security of countries or individuals, promoting decolonization, and insuring the people to utilize natural resources and wealth with sovereignty, it aware of obligation of State under the charter to encourage universal respect for adherence of human right and fundamental freedom without any discrimination of sex, race, caste, place of birth, language, nation, religion, wealth, income and others, it considers the eradication of violation of human right, colonization, neo-colonization, apartheid all other form of racial discrimination and consider the peace and security of nation for assist in right to development, it concerned about that existence hindrance which create problem to enjoyment of social, cultural, political and economic right, it considers reaffirmation of close relationship between demobilization and development for the promotion of right to development and this demobilization should work for the benefit of economic and social well-being of people, it recognizing the state to create a amenable environment for smooth development of state and their individuals, it aware of efforts not only for national instead also for international level, and at last it confirm that right to development is inseparable right for all the countries as well individuals of all the countries.³²

The preamble of the DRTD 1986 deals with the nation and the individual. It does not leave any country or individual to avail of these rights, and it even imposes an obligation on the state not to create any hindrance or barrier for other countries. Its primary focus is not only on the development of relatively sustainable development, but also on enjoying these rights without any annoyance, which creates a barrier to the enjoyment of these indispensable rights.

The nature of the right to development is enshrined in the first article of the DRTD 1986, and it also shows on which principle it was adopted.³³ It says that the right to development is an inseparable human right, as a result of which all human beings are entitled to enjoy economic,

³² United Nations General Assembly, *Declaration on the Right to Development* UNGA Res 41/128 (4 December 1986) preamble.

³³ Teshome R G, „The Draft Convention on the Right to Development: A New Dawn to the Recognition of the Right to Development as a Human Right?“ (2022) 22 *HRLR* 1, 3.

social, cultural, and political rights without any barrier or hindrance, and the second part gives the right of enjoyment of all natural resources and natural wealth with complete sovereignty.³⁴ This article does not specify any specific individual group; instead, it guarantees human beings the right to enjoy their rights, subject to other legal provisions and the International Covenant.

The primary subject matter of the right to development is human beings, and they should actively participate in the issues that are related to the right to development because they are beneficiaries of DRTD. Human beings also have a duty towards other person, either collectively or individually, for their fundamental economic, social, cultural, and political right, and DRTD also imposes a duty to make policies for the enjoyment of these freedoms and rights without any hindrance or barrier, and also make mechanisms that regulate the rights and freedoms and ensure the principle of DRTD.³⁵

There must be a convenient environment for the right to development, which is the state's responsibility to create such an amenable environment, so that the nation develops at both the national and international levels. The state has kept the principles of the UN Charter and other covenants that were adopted at the global level; state has duty to cooperate with others nation while doing any activity or making any policy with intention to development and also ensure and protect the right of human beings while the taking these measures and also promote the New International Economic Order thereby promote equality, self-independence, reciprocal interest and harmonious relation among the nations.³⁶ The last paragraph of this article shows unity among countries and also promotes the concept of selflessness, which ensures the idea of spirituality.

The state has an obligation to make those policies and take such steps, either collectively or individually, to ensure development at the international level, and the development must be sustainable for the rapid growth of all the countries and ensure international development.³⁷ This article is consistent with the concept of the UN Charter.³⁸ It is evident that the idea of spiritualism, as these provisions do deal with the development of one nation or individual or

³⁴ Declaration on the Right to Development, GA Res 41/128 (4 December 1986) art 1.

³⁵ Declaration on the Right to Development, GA Res 41/128 (4 December 1986) art 2.

³⁶ Declaration on the Right to Development, GA Res 41/128 (4 December 1986) art 3.

³⁷ Declaration on the Right to Development, GA Res 41/128 (4 December 1986) art 4.

³⁸ Charter of the United Nations (adopted 26 June 1945, entered into force 24 October 1945) 1 UNTS XVI, art 56 (Ch IX, International Economic and Social Cooperation).

any specific group, instead, they deal with the development of all the countries, which helps in the growth of the global economy.

State shall take strict action against blatant violation of human right and also take all the incentive measures which prevent discriminations on the basis of race, religion, colour, nation and protect from colonization, aggression, foreign interference and threat against the sovereignty of the country, unity of nation, territorial integrity and also take tremendous measures for eliminate apartheid and ensure fundamental freedom of human beings.³⁹ This provision links human rights and the right to development and ensures that we should not forget human rights while developing because, as per this declaration, development means not mere development but sustainable development.

All states should be advancing, fostering, and nurturing universal respect without any distinction among the people and ensuring fundamental freedom for all human beings and also ensure that human rights are individual and inseparable and their implementation must be subjective along with the civil, political, economic, and cultural rights and state has duty to take a massive action against hindrance which create barrier on enjoyment of fundamental human rights.⁴⁰ This article imposes the duty on the state to take incentive measures against these rights, which assist in achieving the primary goal, that is, the right to development.

The state has an obligation to take any step or make any policy that does not affect maintenance, peace, and integrity, instead promote it at the national and international level, and take all the incentive measures which help to achieve the general goal of disarmament and make a link with development.⁴¹

At the national level, state has duty to take all such measures which promote equal distribution of income and resources amongst the people and to give equal opportunities to all people in access to education, health services, food, housing employment, and just and fair distribution of revenue and take initiative social and economic reform which help in eliminating injustice, and also encouragement of people in all sector.⁴² This ensures that development cannot be made by only one group of people; instead, it involves all sectors of the group.

³⁹ Declaration on the Right to Development, GA Res 41/128 (4 December 1986) art 5.

⁴⁰ Declaration on the Right to Development, GA Res 41/128 (4 December 1986) art 6.

⁴¹ Declaration on the Right to Development, GA Res 41/128 (4 December 1986) art 7.

⁴² Declaration on the Right to Development, GA Res 41/128 (4 December 1986) art 8.

Every facet of DRTD must be taken as a whole, which means the right to development is an indispensable and inseparable right of human beings, and it must be interpreted in accordance with the United Declaration of Human Rights and the International Covenant of Human Rights.⁴³

The state has a duty to make policy and enact laws for the adoption, formation, and implementation of the right to development at the national and international levels.⁴⁴

As we know, the New International Economic Order was adopted on the 1st May 1974 in the UN General Assembly.⁴⁵ The primary purpose of this Order is to promote the World Economy. There are 10 sections given in the New International Economic Order.⁴⁶

The first part of the NIEO deals with the protection of raw materials and fundamental goods from exploitation and focuses on equal distribution of these raw materials and necessary goods without any kind of discrimination, and this order also imposes an obligation on all states to improve transportation and insurance facilities along with a general trade system.⁴⁷

The objective of second part of this Order to maintain the monetary system's balance at International level thereby world economy would not suffer any economic crises and also create good balance of monetary system between developed countries and developing countries and take incentive measures by making policy, promotion of investment, exemption of barriers for import or export and also make policy for International financial Institution which help in achieving the goal of "balance monetary system".⁴⁸

The third part of this Order actually imposes an obligation on developed countries to make favourable conditions for developing countries to invest in the industrial sector, and these provisions give priority to developing countries over developed countries.⁴⁹ This order shows

⁴³ Declaration on the Right to Development, GA Res 41/128 (4 December 1986) art 9.

⁴⁴ Declaration on the Right to Development, GA Res 41/128 (4 December 1986) art 10.

⁴⁵ UNGA "Programme of Action on the Establishment of a New International Economic Order" (S-VI, 1974).

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*

⁴⁷ UNGA Res 3202 (S-VI) „Programme of Action on the Establishment of a New International Economic Order, I. Fundamental Problems of Raw Materials and Primary Commodities as Related to Trade and Development“ (1 May 1974).

⁴⁸ UNGA Res 3202 (S-VI) „Programme of Action on the Establishment of a New International Economic Order, II. International Monetary System and Financing of the Development of Developing Countries“ (1 May 1974).

⁴⁹ UNGA Res 3202 (S-VI) „Programme of Action on the Establishment of a New International Economic Order, III. Industrialization“ (1 May 1974).

the concept of sustainable development. There should be a transfer and access of technology for all nations, which ensures the growth of the world economy while transformation or innovation also protects the resources of the least developed countries.⁵⁰

There should be effort in the area of regulation and implementation of the International Code, which protects the state from interference of other entities and maintains security, and to make amenable conditions for the developing countries, as well as promote them for reinvestment.⁵¹

There should be cooperation and a harmonious relationship between the developing countries at the regional and sub-regional level by making an appropriate mechanism, protecting the indispensable right, increasing economic interconnectedness, considerable condition for import as well as export, create more favourable condition for developing countries, and developed countries should assist at regional and sub-regional level that shall play a role in the new economic order.⁵² Implementing the NIEO in a way that encourages cooperation among the countries in light of building the concept of the United Nations and all its conventions and declarations at the international level.⁵³ All the International norms show that there must be a focus on the growth of the global economy.

V. Challenges of Declaration on The Right to Development and The New International Economic Order

As we know, DRTD and NIEO are not compulsory binding on the state; it is just a declaration that every country should follow, but in practice, we know a minimum number of principles are followed by the nation and a recent example of the imposition of a 50 percent tariff by the US Government on India.⁵⁴ The principle of DRTD says to promote a favourable environment and not directly or indirectly affect the sovereignty of other countries.

⁵⁰ UNGA Res 3202 (S-VI) „Programme of Action on the Establishment of a New International Economic Order, IV. Transfer of Technology“ (1 May 1974).

⁵¹ UNGA Res 3202 (S-VI) „Programme of Action on the Establishment of a New International Economic Order, V. Regulation and Control over the Activities of Transnational Corporations“ (1 May 1974).

⁵² UNGA Res 3202 (S-VI) „Programme of Action on the Establishment of a New International Economic Order, VII. Promotion of Co-operation among Developing Countries“ (1 May 1974).

⁵³ UNGA Res 3202 (S-VI) „Programme of Action on the Establishment of a New International Economic Order, IX. Strengthening the Role of the United Nations System in the Field of International Economic Co-operation“ (1 May 1974).

⁵⁴ India TV, „US issues official notice to impose 25% additional tariffs on India from August 27“ (India TV, 26 August 2025) <https://www.indiatvnews.com/news/world/trump-trade-war-us-issue-official-notice-to-impose-25-additional-tariffs-on-india-from-aug-27-2025-08-26-1005164> accessed 30 August 2025.

There is no provision present in DRTD and NIEO that imposes a sanction for the violation or for not effectively implementing the idea of DRTD and NIEO.⁵⁵ It is evidence of not being strictly binding on the countries that are not following these norms either entirely or partially.

The significant challenges are an imbalance of the natural environment, inequalities in the socio-economic and political sectors, poverty at the global level, and a lack of adequate mutual understanding between the countries. The developed countries play a vital role in tackling these challenges compared to the least developed countries. “The developed countries can also help the LDCs by writing off old debts or putting a moratorium on them. The Third World debt in 1990 stood at approximately 1.3 trillion dollars, which represents approximately 44 per cent of the gross national product of all developing countries combined.”⁵⁶

Both the agricultural and industrial sectors must be driven in a well-planned manner because these are considered the primary parts of a growing economy, and maximum use of fossil fuels could create an imbalance in those countries that are totally dependent on the importation of petroleum. Conventional wisdom also tries to search for alternative sources of natural resources, irrespective of balance of payment issues.⁵⁷

Policy for increasing the supply of energy, water is one of the resources that is in much more demand, among natural resources. For the generation of energy, a power plant is pervasive in its establishment, and continuation requires a significant cost and a river flowing across the country. Interstate cooperation is beneficial for irrigation and the generation of energy, which require minimal input from both states, and they receive maximum output from them.⁵⁸

Transitional corporations and Multinational corporations promote the idea of internationalization, which is also one of the primary objectives of DRTD and NIEO, and these countries are also consuming petroleum, so South countries and Southeast Asian countries' cooperation is a debatable issue.⁵⁹ Monetary system one of the system which play vital role in the world economy and generally they are regulated by International financial institution like

⁵⁵ UNGA Res 41/128 “Declaration on the Right to Development” (4 December 1986). UNGA” Programme of Action on the Establishment of a New International Economic Order” (S-VI, 1 May 1974).

⁵⁶ Dr Priya Saroj and Ms Puja Sharma, „The Major Issues and Means of NIEO, The New International Economic Order (NIEO): Challenges and Perspectives” (2018) *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)* ISSN 2320-2882.

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

⁵⁹ *Ibid.*

International monetary fund and World Bank, these International Financial Institution are typically controlled by those countries which are giving higher contribution and these things either directly or indirectly affect to least developed countries and these things would not resolve unless and until provide some power to least developed countries while policy making.⁶⁰

VI. Conclusion

DRTD and NIEO are the two vital wheels that can make the world free from inequalities, armed conflicts, and environmental pollution, and promote social rights, political rights, economic rights, and cultural rights, along with following the other norms that are adopted at the international level. These provisions promote the idea of globalization, which is also interconnected with the concepts of liberalization and privatization, which play a vital role in the growth of the world economy. They also help those countries that are covered under the category of least developed countries.

After the COVID-19 Pandemic, these ideas have declined. Most countries were in the grip of it, as their economy would collapse; therefore, they are mainly focusing on building their own economic growth, which is evidence of the decline of these ideas.⁶¹ Nowadays, this pandemic problem has arisen, and all the countries' economies are increasing gradually. "The National Statistics Office's (NSO) provisional estimates peg India's gross domestic product (GDP) growth at 6.5 per cent for 2024-25, with the fourth quarter growing at a blistering 7.4 per cent.

The first and second advance estimates, which were based on limited data, had projected 6.4 per cent and 6.5 per cent, respectively. The positive surprises in GDP revisions seen in the past three fiscals may end here, at least for now. The economy seems to be realigning with its long-term trend growth. The decadal average growth before the Covid-19 pandemic was 6.6 per cent."⁶² The growth rate of a country's economy shows what the government did and what it is doing, and in the same way, the growth rate of the world economy shows whether international norms are followed by the countries or not.

⁶⁰ *Ibid.*

⁶¹ Yuefen Li, Daniel Uribe and Danish, 'Conclusions, The International Discourse on the Right to Development and the Need to Reinvigorate its Implementation' (South Centre, 8 March 2022).

⁶² GDP figures show India is back on the road to growth" *The Indian Express* (New Delhi, 2 December 2022) <https://indianexpress.com/article/opinion/columns/gdp-figures-show-india-is-back-on-the-road-to-growth-10042653/> accessed 30 August 2025.